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Survey on current AM applications in accelerators and expected new developments

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ABSTRACT

The present Milestone report deals with the output of a survey on the application of Additive Manufacturing (AM) technologies in the field of particle accelerators. Current applications, further needs and perspective developments foreseen for the accelerator community are discussed.

The document makes a synthesis of the scientific outputs also described in deliverable D10.1. It consists of a first part where a literature survey of existing applications of AM to accelerators has been made. An analysis of the needs for the accelerator community is then presented, followed by a discussion about the opportunities offered by AM for accelerators in particle physics and for technology transfer to accelerators for other industrial fields.

Finally, the design activities, manufacturing and testing of a proof-of-concept RFQ sector built by AM are described. The dissemination of this output to the widest possible audience is considered as an important strategy to raise awareness about advantages of AM in the accelerator community.

I.FAST Consortium, 2023

For more information on IFAST, its partners and contributors please see <https://ifast-project.eu/>

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Executive summary

The report presents a summary of the activities carried out, and of the output achieved, within task 10.2 about the survey on additive manufacturing (AM) applications in accelerators. The main needs for the accelerator community and perspective developments aimed at increasing confidence and awareness about opportunities and limitations offered by the AM technology are discussed. As a Milestone report, the present document is organized through a synthesis of Deliverable D10.1 which described in details the scientific outputs achieved.

In particular, chapter two of the report contains a detailed list of AM applications in the accelerator field, in an attempt to describe potential opportunities and highlight the challenges still to be faced.

Chapter three is aimed at analysing further needs that would speed up the uptake of AM in the community. The outputs of a survey carried out within the frame of a joint activity between task 10.2 and 10.3 of the I.FAST project are briefly recalled. It is concluded that the particle-accelerator community apparently feels the lack of knowledge about specific topics which represent the next challenges to be faced in a near future. These include: materials, with their strict requirements on purity, lack of defects and well known properties; size, geometrical accuracy and surface roughness of the printed parts; other peculiar part properties such as vacuum tightness, outgassing rate, electrical conductivity, high-voltage holding.

Chapter four summarizes the opportunities of AM for accelerators in particle physics and the expected technology transfer to other industrial fields of societal importance. A further section describes the outputs of activities, currently in progress, to stimulate the interest and raise awareness about advantages of AM in the accelerator community. Specifically, the research team has been engaged in the design, manufacturing, and characterisation of a radio-frequency quadrupole proof of concepts manufactured as copper single parts by an innovative Laser-powder bed fusion AM technology based on a green laser source. Promising results have been collected and directions for future development have been identified.

Finally, perspective developments are discussed, highlighting the expected innovations which will become available in the near future on the market, with the hope of stimulating a shift of AM components for accelerators from the prototyping to the production stage.

1 Introduction

Additive Manufacturing (AM) is a recent and fast-evolving technology which is promptly becoming an integral part of the advanced technological portfolio available for the most demanding industrial applications. Within the accelerator community, AM is apparently progressing at a slow pace, owing to traditionalism, lack of knowledge, and skepticism about the compliance with the stringent accelerator requirements.

The present document summarizes the output of activities carried out within task 10.2 (Additive Manufacturing – Survey of applications and potential developments) of the I.FAST project. The main objectives of the task consist in identifying the needs for future and faster development, identifying technology barriers and challenges, and defining the future strategic directions to foster the impact of AM on accelerator applications.

2 Survey of existing AM applications

2.1 LITERATURE SURVEY

A comprehensive list of the of the open literature published over the years about application of AM to accelerator components has been provided in delilverable D10.1. From a quantitative perspective, it can be observed that the number of papers covering AM-related topics yearly published, progressively increased along the years. A further evidence about the increasing interest in AM by the accelerator community can be evaluated through the number of contributions dealing with AM presented in the most recent years at the IPAC conference series: 0 papers in 2019 and 2020, 3 in 2021, 3 in 2022, 12 in 2023.

2.2 REVIEW OF AM APPLICATIONS IN ACCELERATORS

A synthesis was subsequently carried out to describe the already existing accelerator components built by AM. This review will also be published in a more detailed form in [1].

To the authors' knowledge, the first application of metal AM in the accelerator sector (or nuclear physics, in broad terms) appeared in 2005, when a prototype was produced by DED for the ARIES Compact Stellarator coil structure shown in figure 1. The initial aim was to build a cost-effective shell for the magnet coil winding [1,2]. It was claimed that the final cost of the AM part was less than one-third the cost of the same structure manufactured by the conventional route.

Figure 1. ARIES-CS Stellarator coil structure without and with coils in the internal grooves [3].

Soon after the ARIES-CS Stellarator appearance, a patent was filed in the US for the manufacturing of radiofrequency cavities where “the wall of the conductive housing is made by a metal additive manufacturing technique in such a way as to produce a flow path that has a gentle trajectory without discontinuities in gradient” [4].

Frigola and co-workers, in a joint research carried out at RadiaBeam Technologies, UCLA and INFN, considered the AM technology for the design of RF photoinjectors with integrated cooling channels and improved geometry, as shown in figure 2. The output of the research was first presented at EPAC 2008 conference for a RF Gun with 100 Hz repetition rate [5] and at EPAC 2009 [6] for a 500-Hz improved version.

Figure 2. Quarter section of an RF Gun with star-shaped conformal cooling channels and snake-like channels at the coupling window shown in the inset [7].

In 2012 a new design concept for a high-precision fast wire scanner for tests in the Super Proton Synchrotron accelerator at CERN was presented. The proposal suggested the use of metal AM for the manufacturing of the beam scanning forks which support the wire, considering the requirements of lightweight and stiffness (figure 3). The technological development and qualification of the process and the manufactured prototypes were then presented in 2015 [8].

Figure 3. General view of the designed beam wire scanner (left) and details about the design of the forks (right) [9,10].

Analysing the CERN’s Indico server, it appears that the first evidence of an invited lecture dedicated to AM was given by Kilburn from 3T RPD Ltd in 2012 [11]. Few ideas about potential applications in accelerators were already cited in that presentation and many other prototypes were developed in the following years at CERN, as summarized in the lecture given by Sahner of the Mechanical & Materials Engineering group [12]. The main parts manufactured by AM were titanium spacers for MQXC coils (figure 4), LHC Nb-Ti and high-field Nb₃Sn magnets, and high-temperature superconductors HTS.

In the following years, several projects based on development and manufacturing of parts by AM were activated in the European accelerator community. Among others, during the CLIC14 workshop, Grudiev presented the additively manufactured Ti6Al4V WR90 wave-guide demonstrator depicted in figure 5 [13]. It is to note that extensive testing on the printed AM samples was presented such as: DC conductivity, RF loss, leak tightness, outgassing, shape accuracy, surface roughness, mechanical strength and microstructure.

Figure 4. Additive manufactured Ti end-spacers for MQXC coils [11].

Figure 5. Additively manufactured Ti6Al4V waveguide prototype (above) and concept idea of the part (below) implementing a cooling chamber for high-power tests [13].

Further development led to the manufacturing and testing of an improved version, also shown in figure 5 featuring an extra cooling jacket, increased wall thickness, vacuum flanges, using different materials (e.g. 316L stainless steels and Ti-6Al-4V alloy) and comparing two AM processes (e.g. PBF-LB with PBF-EB) [14]. The output suggested that the electron-beam based technology was not as mature as the laser-beam technology. Moreover, issues about surface roughness and geometrical tolerances were identified as the next challenges to face for part validation [13].

In the following years the CLIC RF group at CERN published various research reports showing the results progressively achieved. An instructive survey of the developments carried out through AM for a number of RF X-band components capable to perform in high power was reported by Catalan-Lasheras and co-workers at IPAC18 conference [15]. In addition, the development of X-band spiral load was presented at IPAC2021 by Bursali [16], which eventually led to a concept for the production of RF spiral loads. A view of the spiral load is depicted in figure 6.

Figure 6. RF spiral load (cross-sectional and full model views) designed for AM production [16].

The growing interest on AM for less-conventional materials such as copper and niobium for accelerator components is confirmed by papers published already in 2014 on pure copper and on Niobium. In particular, Frigola et al. [17] produced by the PBF-EB technology copper cathodes for UCLA Pegasus 1.6 cell Photoinjector. Terrazas et al. filed a patent in US about the use of AM for SRF components of various geometries [18] and in the same year published a report on fabrication and characterization of high-purity Nb for superconductor applications claiming that AM technology was a promising alternative to conventional forming, leading to significant advantages for uniform wall thicknesses, improved structure rigidity and material purity [19].

More detailed information about the performance of a RF single cavity based on Fermilab's 3.9 GHz 3rd harmonic cavity design and incorporating stiffening 3D lattice supports (see figure 7) was reported in [20,21]. However, it is to remark that the part was still made by two parts and the process included additional steps of internal surface machining, polishing and final EB welding.

In 2014 a first event fully dedicated to AM topics was organized at CERN [22]. The AM workshop was split into two sessions about metal powders and about polymers & substrates, gathering a total of 115 attendees, with a broad range of talks covering materials, processing and applications.

Further typical applications where opportunities offered by AM can be more efficiently exploited are given by heat exchangers. In 2015, the WP3 research team of the LIEBE project considered the advantages of metal AM for the design and manufacturing of lead-bismuth/water heat exchangers, eventually proposing the prototype depicted in figure 8 [23].

Figure 7. view of the single-cell cavity produced by and produced by PBF-EB technology [20].

Figure 8. Additively manufactured lead-bismuth eutectic/water heat exchanger [23].

Over the years, the increased awareness about AM potential applications, also rose the request for more accurate characterization of material behaviour after AM processing. The testing facilities and protocols available at CERN have been documented in [24,25]. Specific studies to prove vacuum tightness of part produced by PBF-LB have been carried out by French scientists from LAL and CNRS/IN2P3. Type DN40KF tubes produced by two different manufacturers with 316L stainless steels by PBF-LB showed promising results [26]. In a following step, beam pipe monitors featuring

a more complex shape (figure 9) were designed and tested to prove the effectiveness of AM processing for such parts requiring high alignment tolerances [27].

Figure 9. Additively manufactured DN40KF tubes for vacuum tests (left) [26] and BPM prototypes (right) [27].

A dedicated test for vacuum tightness and outgassing using the membranes (ISO KF or CF type) shown in figure 10 is also in use at CERN. The first review of applicability for AM materials was reported in 2016 [25]. Tests carried out on AM printed membranes made of different materials [28] showed that in general stainless steel 316L is helium leak tight with thicknesses exceeding 0,25mm, Ti and Al post-processed by hot isostatic pressing (HIP) are helium tight only above 0,5mm. However, it was observed that these limits are strongly influenced by the manufacturing process and printing parameters.

Figure 10. AM ISO-KF type vacuum test membrane 3D model, drawing and test assembly. [25].

Beam dumps represent a further application in the accelerator field where the design can benefit from opportunities offered by AM. Beam dumps are designed to stop the proton beam of a cyclotron at the end of a beamline. As such, they need to include water cooling channels to control the working temperature. In 2018, INFN DIAM successfully developed beam dump prototypes with internal cooling channels made of pure copper, as depicted in figure 11 [29,30].

The CERN team RADIATE introduced in 2018 a new design of AD target. The new design showed several advantages over the old version, consisting in a larger core diameter, the use of a multi material configuration (Ta, Ir) and expanded graphite as matrix material. Similarly to the above beam dumps, the design included a double wall Ti-6Al-4V assembly with an internal spiral channel for pressurized compressed air cooling [10,31]. The new targets produced by PBF-LB technology at CERN's AM workshop are shown figure 12.

Figure 11. AM pure copper beam dump prototype [30].

Figure 12. Ti-6Al-4V PROTAD target housings produced by PBF-LB [10].

Finally, it is worth recalling that task 10.4 of I.FAST project also foresees the manufacturing of SRF cavities using the PBF-LB technology. These activities have been reported in deliverable D10.3 “Additive-manufactured SRF Cavities” by the lead partner DIAM (INFN Padua Division).

The main aim of the task was to evaluate AM reliability for the manufacturing of seamless 6 GHz SRF cavities. Among others, complete pure-copper cavities could be produced (see figure 13) without internal supports and with flanges at their edges to perform leak tests, cryogenic tests and for surface finishing optimization.

Figure 13. Copper (left) and Niobium (right) SRF cavities produced by L-PBF at DIAM-INFN within the activities of task 10.4 (pictures adapted from Deliverable D10.3).

Niobium samples and cavity prototypes were then developed. With the aim of improving the as built downward-facing surface quality, contour parameters and innovative contactless support structures were investigated, eventually allowing the successful printing of the pure-Niobium cavities also shown in figure 13.

3 Analysis of needs for the accelerator community

3.1 QUESTIONNAIRE ABOUT USE OF AM IN ACCELERATOR COMPONENTS

Within the frame of a joint activity between task 10.2 and 10.3 of the IFAST project, a questionnaire has been spread toward the accelerator community to evaluate the current confidence, concerns and needs for the production and repair of accelerator components. The output of this investigation has already been described in Deliverable D10.2: “Survey of AM applications and strategies for repairing components by AM” submitted in April 2023. Only the most relevant issues will be recalled in this report to support further analyses.

It is worth considering that the questionnaire was circulated through the IFAST project newsletter to 290 project members from 49 participating institutions and 32 associate partners in 14 countries in March 2022. After three months, the feedback was limited to 21 responses, corresponding to a 7,2% response rate.

Data showed that the participants were mainly accelerator-hardware experts or designers and they were already aware about the opportunities offered by AM. When enquiring whether they would consider AM for the manufacturing of accelerator components, 81% replied positively while 9% suggested that AM could be an option only for the future. A long list of accelerator components which might benefit from AM was identified, which includes most of the parts already described in section 2.2, e.g.: cavities, drift tubes, complex shapes with cooling circuits and heat exchangers, supports for sensors and magnets. Considering the expected challenges, material properties, final cost, control of surface roughness and porosity were the concerns most frequently cited.

In conclusion, it was inferred that the accelerator community is being carefully considering AM (both for manufacturing and repair of components), but it is not yet fully enthusiastic about current achievements. There exists a wide list of already-identified components which would potentially benefit from the advantages offered by AM such as design freedom, manufacturing flexibility and processing ability of otherwise critical materials. However, few objective technical challenges, together with a sort of traditionalism and reluctance to change design paradigms, still represent barriers for the uptake of AM.

3.2 ACTIONS TO RAISE CONFIDENCE IN AM

From the above-described investigation, it appears that the field of particle accelerator is looking at AM technologies with great attention, but the number of tested and validated accelerator parts produced by AM is still limited and it is growing at slower rate than for the other similar sectors already cited. There exists a fair awareness that AM is not a “magic tool” for any technical concern since it can offer advantages but also challenges. The AM technology is continuously improving, making available advanced machines with larger build volumes and almost fully automated processes, new software tools for the so-called “design for additive manufacturing” and for accurate process simulation.

However, the particle-accelerator community apparently feels the lack of knowledge about specific topics which represent the next challenges to be faced in a near future to raise confidence and reduce skepticism in AM. They can be grouped into the following three key points.

- Materials for most accelerator components have strict chemical-purity requirements, they must show uniform microstructure, lack of manufacturing defects, residual stresses and well-known properties.
- The size of components may exceed the printing volume of many AM commercial systems while the requirements for geometrical accuracy and surface roughness of accelerator parts are often very demanding for most of the available AM processes.
- Peculiar material/part properties need to be carefully characterized before applications in particle accelerators, such as vacuum tightness, outgassing rate, electrical conductivity, high-voltage holding.

The analysis of the most recent literature and of the existing research projects running in Europe and worldwide confirms that the above technical gaps are being filled by virtue of the large efforts dedicated. In line with these needs, a significant contribution is being created also by the AM-group established within the partners of I.FAST WP10.

4 Potential AM applications in accelerators

4.1 OPPORTUNITIES FOR ACCELERATORS IN PARTICLE PHYSICS AND TECHNOLOGY TRANSFER TO OTHER INDUSTRIAL FIELDS

AM, with its multiple processing variants, including powder bed fusion, directed energy deposition and bound metal deposition technologies, is currently attracting a large interest for industrial applications in several sectors such as aerospace, medical, power generation, which very often feature demanding technical and safety requirements.

As stated, although with a slower pace, the accelerator community is also approaching AM. Components for large infrastructures in particle physics where design and manufacturing opportunities provided by AM can be exploited at best are for instance cavities, supports for sensors and magnets, cooling systems and manifolds with complex shapes, synchrotron radiation absorbers, particles sources and targets, RF guns and quadrupoles. For all of them, the most attractive opportunities consist in the ability to design new and optimized shapes which were considered as impossible to be produced by conventional manufacturing routes, along with the possible reduction of costs and usage of precious materials, and the shorter lead times. A proof-of-concept implementing these features will be described in the next section.

In addition, AM is implicitly supporting strategies toward the development of compact, more accessible and better performing accelerators to be used commercially to improve and sustain the quality of our life. Medical equipment for cancer radiation therapies (proton- and ion-therapy) and for the production of isotopes for imaging and nuclear medicine would greatly benefit from innovations in compact accelerators. Other industrial sectors for accelerators involve the sterilization for medical disposables and for food processing, the non-destructive testing of machine components by X-rays and γ -rays, the safety inspections of containers loaded on cargos, the treatments on fumes and exhaust gases to reduce the amount of pollutants.

4.2 DEVELOPMENT AND TESTING OF A RFQ FOR ACCELERATORS

Modern 4-vane type RFQs are conventionally manufactured by highly-conductive oxygen-free copper by multi-axis high-precision milling of pre-fabricated large-scale forged workpieces. The full section of a RFQ generally consists of four modules (see figure 14) with complex and high-tolerance manufactured surfaces that are subsequently joined together in the final 4-vane configuration by furnace brazing. A complex procedure requiring several thermal stress-release treatments during the machining steps is required to ensure that the tight tolerances are respected even after brazing. This results in a costly, time consuming, and inefficient process.

Figure 14. The CERN's LINAC 4 RFQ module [32].

It was realized that the opportunities offered by AM would be particularly suitable to improve the manufacturing aspects of RFQs by significantly reducing manufacturing time and costs and implementing improved design criteria. Eventually, complete segments including all the four vanes of the RFQ system could be built in one piece, thereby avoiding brazing and allowing for the optimal manufacturing of complex elements such as internal cooling channels and external ports [32]. RFQ manufacturing also features several strict requirements which make the development of an AM prototype rather challenging. These are summarized in table 1.

Table 1. Main technical requirements for the RFQ prototype [32].

Requirement	Target value
Geometrical accuracy	20 μm on vane tip, 100 μm elsewhere
Surface roughness	Ra = 0,4 μm for all inner surfaces
Vacuum tightness	10^{-7} mbar
Electrical conductivity	90% IACS
Peak electric field on surface	≈ 40 MV/m

For these reasons, a RFQ prototype to be produced by AM (specifically by PBF-LB) was designed, produced and subjected to functional tests within the activities of task 10.2 of IFAST project.

To the authors' knowledge, the output represents the very first proof-of-concept confirming that AM manufactured RFQs are feasible and achievable. Its dissemination to the widest possible audience was considered to be an important strategy to raise awareness about advantages of AM in the accelerator community.

A first proof-of-concept of the RFQ was intended to reproduce one quarter of a compact 750 MHz RFQ reaching the energy of 5MeV in a length of 2 meters, which was recently developed at CERN for applications in the medical and detection fields [33]. A model of the RFQ quarter with a length of 95 mm was designed based on AM manufacturing capabilities and opportunities. The RFQ shows a quadrupolar symmetry, therefore, all peculiar features can be included within a 90° sector design, as shown in figure 15. The quarter-sector prototype includes the vane tip reproducing the original design geometry, the inner surfaces, and a re-designed inner structure implementing conformal cooling channels to optimize the thermal service conditions and consisting of a honeycomb pattern which replaces the original massive sections.

Figure 15. RFQ quarter section designed for AM [32].

Full details about the design have been published in [32]. The proof-of-concept was built by project partner Fraunhofer IWS with pure copper, using a TruPrint1000 Green Edition PBF-LB system equipped with a green laser providing a wavelength of 515 nm (more suitable to maximize the laser absorption for copper) and a maximum laser power of 500 W. The 3D print job took 16 hours and 29 minutes for a total height of 98 mm, produced by 3267 print layers of thickness 30 μm each.

Based on the investigation carried out on the first quarter RFQ proof of concept, two full-size RFQ sectors were subsequently designed, implementing a set of improved features and a size compatible with current compact linear accelerator RFQs.

Figure 16. Full-size RFQ design (left) and view of the printed part [34].

Figure 17. View of the as built second full-size RFQ (source: www.trumpf.cn/en_CN/products/machines-systems/additive-production-systems/truprint-5000-green-edition) and a detail of the printed part.

The copper RFQ demonstrators have been printed with a new model TruPrint 5000 PBF-LB system recently launched on the market by project partner TRUMPF. The system features a green laser source and a larger process chamber allowing to build volumes of 300 mm in diameter and 400 mm in height. A first full-section RFQ segment was produced with a total length of 248 mm and a cross-section diameter of 148 mm, as described in [34]. The print process took about 110 hours for a total of about 6400 layers of 40 μm thickness each. The new design takes advantage of an improved high-resolution CAD model, optimized shape of the cooling channels and of the internal lattice structure. It implements flanges for vacuum tests and orifices and for RF tests. Figure 16 depicts the design of the RFQ sector and the corresponding printed workpiece. In a further stage, a second full-size RFQ sector with slightly larger length was produced, as shown in figure 17.

The two demonstrators are currently under investigation to complete a first set of processing and performance tests. One of the samples has been subjected to surface polishing, machining of some functional surfaces (flange planes, basal planes, bores for connections) and will be tested for vacuum tightness and RF at IJCLab. To increase confidence and awareness about potential opportunities provided by AM for accelerator components, additional information is required especially on performance of the printed materials. With this objective, pure-copper samples have separately been printed for microstructure characterization, high-voltage tests and He gas tightness. Preliminary results have already been published in [35,36].

5 Perspective developments

The described analyses and surveys undoubtedly show that the community of particle accelerator is paying great attention to AM technologies, with increasing knowledge about advantages to be exploited and challenges to be faced.

The activities carried out within tasks 10.2, 10.3 and 10.4 of the IFAST project are also contributing to attract the “curiosity” of the accelerator community and are promoting synergies among all actors having interest/activities in AM for accelerators. In particular, experimental activities are running within task 10.2 on the RFQ printed by PBF-LB (described in section 4.2). Repair technologies using AM concepts are being investigated within task 10.3, and cavities are under development in task 10.4. These actions are generally aimed at improving knowledge and confidence in AM, to fight skepticism of the most traditional designers

In a broader perspective, it can be observed that the AM technology is continuously improving, making available on the market advanced machines with larger build volumes and almost fully automated processes, new software tools to support the so-called “design for additive manufacturing” and for accurate process simulation. Research is addressing the strategic topics of multi-material AM and of hybrid manufacturing (additive + subtractive within a single machine) to offer additional degree of freedom in the design of advanced components.

Such developments are expected to stimulate new designs of accelerator components and will hopefully provide new ideas for the submission of joint research projects by the scientific community, with the final goal of shifting AM from the prototyping to production and application stage.

6 Conclusion

The main conclusions about the survey on current applications of Additive Manufacturing (AM) in particle accelerators and about the expected developments, can be summarized as follows.

- The literature shows that AM applications in accelerators exist since 2005 and they are significantly growing in the most recent years. They typically include: cavities, drift tubes, complex shapes with cooling circuits and heat exchangers, supports for sensors and magnets. The adoption of AM to these parts provides advantages such as: design freedom, manufacturing flexibility and processing ability of otherwise critical materials.
- A survey has been made toward the accelerator community to evaluate the current confidence, concerns and needs for the production and repair of accelerator components. Hardware experts and accelerator-designers are already aware about the opportunities offered by AM. Most of them would currently consider AM for the manufacturing of accelerator components, while a small share (9%) considers AM as an option, but only for the future.
- The particle-accelerator community apparently feels the lack of knowledge about specific topics which represent the next challenges to be faced in the near future to raise confidence and reduce scepticism in AM: (i) materials for most accelerator components have strict requirements and need accurate characterization after being processed by AM; (ii) the size of components may exceed the printing volume while the requirements for geometrical accuracy and surface roughness of accelerator parts are often very demanding for the state-of-the-art of AM commercial systems; (iii) specific material/part properties need to be carefully characterized before applications in particle accelerators, such as vacuum tightness, outgassing rate, electrical conductivity, high-voltage holding.
- These technical gaps are being progressively filled by virtue of the large research efforts dedicated. In line with these needs, a contribution is being created also by the AM-group established within the partners of I.FAST WP10. A proof-of-concept for a RFQ sector was designed, manufactured by PBF-LB and it is currently at the testing and evaluation stage. To the authors' knowledge, this output represents the very first proof-of-concept confirming that AM-manufactured RFQ is feasible and achievable. Its dissemination to the widest possible audience is considered as an important strategy to raise awareness about advantages of AM in the accelerator community.
- The adoption of AM also suggests innovative strategies toward the development of compact, more accessible, and better performing accelerators to be used commercially to improve and sustain the quality of our life. Medical equipment for cancer radiation therapies, sterilization of devices and food processing, non-destructive testing and safety inspections, treatments of fumes and exhaust gases to reduce pollutants, are only few examples of sectors which would greatly benefit from innovations in compact accelerators.

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Annex: Glossary

Acronym	Definition
AM	Additive Manufacturing
BJ	Binder Jetting
CLIC	Compact Linear Collider
DED	Directed Energy Deposition
DMLS	Direct Metal Laser Sintering
HIP	Hot Isostatic Pressing
LHC	Large Hadron Collider
PBF-LB	Powder Bed Fusion by Laser Beam
PBF-EB	Powder Bed Fusion by Electron Beam
RF	Radio Frequency
RFQ	Radio-Frequency Quadrupole
SLA	StereoLitography (Apparatus)
SLS	Selective Laser Sintering
SRF	Superconducting Radio Frequency
UHV	Ultra-High Vacuum